

**KESIK SFERIK DISKLI CHIZIQLI-POG‘ONASIMON PLUGNING TORTISHGA
QARSHILIGI HISOBLASH**

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Annatasiya: Kesik sferik diskli chiziqli-pog‘onasimon plugning umumiy tortishga qarshiligi disksimon pichoqlar, korpuslar, tuproqchuqurlatkichlar va kesik sferik disklarning tortishga qarshiliklari yig‘indisi aniqlandi.

Kalit so‘zlar: nishablik, kesik, sferik disk, plug, tortishga qarshiligi disksimon pichoq, korpuslar, tuproqchuqurlatkich.

**CALCULATION OF THE TENSIONAL RESISTANCE OF A LINEAR-STEP PLUG WITH A
CUT SPHERICAL DISC**

Abstract: The total traction resistance of linear-step plow with truncated spherical disc was determined as the sum of the traction resistances of disc blades, housings, soil deepeners and truncated spherical discs.

Keywords: slope, cross section, spherical disk, plug, traction resistance disk blade, casings, soil dredging.

Kirish. Nishabli dalalarga ishlov beradigan plugga quyiladigan agrotexnika talablaridan kelib chiqib, suv eroziyasiga qarshi nishabli dalalarni shudgorlashning takomillashgan texnologiyasi va dala yuzasida uzlukli ariqlar hamda o‘rkachlar hosil qiladigan kesik diskli chiziqli pog‘onasimon plugning konstruktiv sxemasi ishlab chiqildi.

Texnologiyada avval palaxsalar o‘z egati chegarasida 180°ga ag‘dariladi, shudgor tubi yo‘l-yo‘l yumshatiladi, so‘ngra shudgor yuzasida o‘rkachlar va uzlukli ariqlar hosil qilinadi, ya‘ni ariqlar ichida to‘siqlar shakllantiriladi.

Tahlil va natijalar: Kesik sferik diskli chiziqli-pog‘onasimon plugning umumiy tortishga qarshiligi disksimon pichoqlar, korpuslar, tuproqchuqurlatkichlar va kesik sferik disklarning tortishga qarshiliklari yig‘indisidan iborat

$$P_{nl} = n_{\partial} R_{\partial x} + n_{\kappa} P_{\kappa 3x} + n_{\psi o} R_{\psi o} + n_{\kappa \partial} R_{\kappa \partial} + Q_x, \quad (1)$$

Disksimon pichoqning tortishga qarshiligini quyidagi ifoda bo‘yicha aniqlash mumkin [1].

$$R_{\partial x} = K_{\partial} a_{\kappa \partial}, \quad (2)$$

Tayanch g‘ildiragining Q_x qarshilik kuchi esa quyidagiga teng

$$Q_x = \mu Q_z, \quad (3)$$

Zaplujnikli korpusning umumiy tortishga qarshiligi korpus, zaplujnik va dala taxtalarining tortishga qarshiliklari yig‘indisidan iborat

$$P_{\kappa 3x} = R_{\kappa x} + R_{3x} + F_x = P_{\kappa x} + F_x, \quad (4)$$

Zaplujnikli korpusning tortishga qarshiligi korpus va zaplujniklarning tortishga qarshiliklari yig‘indisidan iborat, ya‘ni

$$P_{\kappa x} = R_{\kappa x} + R_{3x}. \quad (5)$$

Korpusning tortishga qarshiligini quyidagi ma‘lum ifoda orqali aniqlaymiz

$$R_{\kappa x} = \eta K a_{\kappa} b_{\kappa}, \quad (6)$$

Y.P.Lobachevskiy, V.V.Sharov va S.A.Zolotarevlarning olib borgan tajribaviy tadqiqotlariga ko‘ra, zaplujnikning tortishga qarshiligi zaplujnikli korpusning qarshiligining 20-24% ni tashkil qiladi [2, 3, 4], ya‘ni

$$R_{3x} = (0,2 - 0,24) P_{\kappa x}, \quad (7)$$

$$R_{\kappa x} = (0,76 - 0,8) P_{\kappa x}. \quad (8)$$

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqqan holda qabul qilamiz

$$R_{\kappa\kappa} = \frac{\eta K a_{\kappa} b_{\kappa}}{0,8}, \quad (9)$$

$$R_{3x} = \frac{1}{4} \eta K a_{\kappa} b_{\kappa}, \quad (10)$$

Korpus va zaplujnikka ta'sir etuvchi reaksiya kuchlarining ko'ndalang tashkil etuvchilarini quyidagi ifodalar orqali aniqlaymiz [5].

$$R_{3y} = R_{3x} \operatorname{ctg}(\gamma_3 + \varphi), \quad (11)$$

$$R_{\kappa y} = R_{\kappa x} \operatorname{ctg}(\gamma + \varphi), \quad (12)$$

Dala taxtasiga ta'sir etuvchi reaksiya kuchlarining bo'ylama va ko'ndalang tashkil etuvchilarini quyidagi ifodalar orqali aniqlash mumkin [1, 5].

$$F_y = R_{\kappa y} - R_{3y}, \quad (13)$$

$$F_x = f F_y = f(R_{\kappa y} - R_{3y}). \quad (14)$$

$R_{\kappa y}$ va R_{3y} larning qiymatlarini (11) va (12) bo'yicha (13) ifodalarga quyib F_x ni aniqlash uchun quyidagi ifodani olamiz

$$F_x = f \eta K a_{\kappa} b_{\kappa} [\operatorname{ctg}(\gamma + \varphi) + \frac{1}{4} \operatorname{ctg}(\gamma_3 + \varphi)]. \quad (15)$$

$P_{\kappa x}$ va F_x larning qiymatlarini (13) va (14) bo'yicha (15) ifodaga quyib bitta zaplujnikli korpusning umumiy tortishga qarshiligi $P_{\kappa x}$ ni aniqlash uchun quyidagi ifodani olamiz

$$P_{\kappa x} = \frac{\eta K a_{\kappa} b_{\kappa}}{0,8} + f \eta K a_{\kappa} b_{\kappa} [\operatorname{ctg}(\gamma + \varphi) + \frac{1}{4} \operatorname{ctg}(\gamma_3 + \varphi)]. \quad (16)$$

Tuproqchuqurlatkichning tortishga qarshilik kuchini aniqlash uchun V.P.Goryachkinning rasional formulasidan foydalanamiz [6].

$$R_{uo} = F(K_u + \varepsilon_u V_n^2), \quad (17)$$

1- rasmga asosan

$$F = a_{io} b_u + a_{io}^2 \operatorname{ctg} \psi, \quad (18)$$

F ning qiymatini (18) bo'yicha (19) ifodaga quyib olamiz

$$R_{uo} = (a_{io} b_u + a_{io}^2 \operatorname{ctg} \psi)(K_u + \varepsilon_u V_n^2). \quad (19)$$

Bitta sferik diskni tortishga qarshilik kuchini aniqlash uchun V.P.Goryachkinning rasional formulasidan foydalanamiz [6]

$$R_{\kappa d} = S(K_1 + \varepsilon_1 V^2), \quad (20)$$

S ning qiymatini (20) ifoda bo'yicha (21) ifodaga quyib olamiz

$$P_{\kappa d} = \left\{ \left(a_{\kappa d} - \frac{D}{2} \right) \sqrt{a_{\kappa d} (D - a_{\kappa d})} + \frac{D^2}{4} \left[\arcsin \left(\frac{2a_{\kappa d}}{D} - 1 \right) + \frac{\pi}{2} \right] \right\} x \quad (21)$$

$$x \sin \alpha (K_1 + \varepsilon_1 V^2).$$

$a_{\kappa d} = 0,12$ m, $R = 0,23$ m, $\alpha = 30^\circ$, $K_1 = 0,65$ kPa, $\varepsilon_1 = 2 \cdot 10^2$ Nc²/m⁴ deb qabul qilib, (2.58) ifoda bo'yicha o'tkazilgan hisoblar 1,67-2,22 m/s tezlik oralig'ida bitta diskning tortishga qarshiligi 110-121 N ni tashkil etishini ko'rsatdi.

$R_{\kappa x}$, $P_{\kappa x}$, R_{ux} , $R_{\kappa d}$ va Q_x larning qiymatlarini (2), (3), (16), (19) va (21) ifodalar bo'yicha (1) ga quyib olamiz

$$\begin{aligned} P_{ni} = & n_o K_o a_o + n_{\kappa} \left\{ \frac{\eta K a_{\kappa} b_{\kappa}}{0,8} + f \eta K a_{\kappa} b_{\kappa} [\operatorname{ctg}(\gamma + \varphi) + \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{4} \operatorname{ctg}(\gamma_3 + \varphi)] \right\} + n_{uo} (a_{io} b_u + a_{io}^2 \operatorname{ctg} \psi_1)(K_u + \varepsilon_u V_n^2) + \\ & + n_{\kappa d} \left\{ \left(a_{\kappa d} - \frac{D}{2} \sqrt{a_{\kappa d} (D - a_{\kappa d})} + \frac{D^2}{4} \left[\arcsin \left(\frac{2a_{\kappa d}}{D} - 1 \right) + \frac{\pi}{2} \right] \right\} x \right. \\ & \left. x \sin \alpha (K_1 + \varepsilon_1 V^2) + \mu Q_z. \right. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

$n_d=3$, $a_d=0,11$ m, $K_d=0,8$ kPa, $n_k=4$, $\eta=0,7$, $f=0,5$, $n_{kd}=2$, $a_{kd}=0,12$ m, $R=0,23$ m, $\alpha=30^\circ$, $K=45$ kPa, $n_{yu}=2$, $a_{yu}=0,12$ m, $b_u=0,05$ m, $K_u=15$ kPa, $\varepsilon_u=8 \cdot 10^2$ Ns²/m⁴, $K_1=0,65$ kPa, $\varepsilon_1=2 \cdot 10^2$ Ns²/m⁴, $a_k=0,24$ m, $b_k=0,45$ m, $\varphi=25^\circ$, $\gamma=42^\circ$, $\gamma_s=30^\circ$, $\psi=45^\circ$, $\mu=0,2$ va $Q_z=11$ kN qabul qilinib, (22) ifoda bo'yicha o'tkazilgan hisoblar 1,67-2,22 m/s tezlik oralig'ida kesik diskli chiziqli-pog'onasimon plugning tortishga qarshiligi 24,7-24,9 kN ni tashkil etishini ko'rsatdi.

Yuqoridagi ifodalar tahliliga ko'ra kesik disklarning tortishga qarshiligi plugning tortishga qarshiligiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmaydi.

Xulosa.

O'tkazilgan nazariy tadqiqotlar natijalari kesik sferik diskning diametri 420-490 mm oralig'ida, disk kesigi sektorining minimal burchagi 42°, sektorining chuqurligi 10 cm va harakat yo'nalishiga nisbatan o'rnatilish burchagi 28-32° oralig'ida, kesik sferik disk bilan korpus orasidagi minimal bo'ylama masofa 110 cm, ko'ndalang masofa esa 15 cm bo'lishi lozimligini ko'rsatdi.

O'tkazilgan hisoblar natijalariga ko'ra kesik sferik diskning tortishga qarshiligi 1,67-2,22 m/s tezlik oralig'ida 110-121 N ni, kesik diskli pog'onasimon plugning tortishga umumiy qarshiligi esa 24,7-24,9 kN ni tashkil etadi.

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